

ROLE OF SUTIKA PARICHARYA IN PREVENTING SUTIKA KATISHULA

¹Dr. Prashant Patil, ²*Dr. Vama Sanghvi

¹HOD and Professor, SMBT Ayurved College, Dhamangaon, Nashik.

²3 Year PG Student, SMBT Ayurved College, Dhamangaon, Nashik.

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*Corresponding Author

Dr. Vama Sanghvi

3 Year PG Student, SMBT
Ayurved College,
Dhamangaon, Nashik.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to Kashyap, though woman has given to birth to fetus, only after expulsion of placenta, can be termed as Sutika.^[1] The management of Sutika has been mentioned in Ayurveda, but Acharya Kashyap has described it. In the postpartum phase, he included katishula as one of the sutika disease.

Due to Pravahana and Raktakshay, all Doshas become agitated in Sutikavastha, but Vata dosha is particularly affected. Sutikavastha is not a diseased condition, but caused due to Agnimandya, Vataprakopa, and Dhatukshaya. Katishool in Sutika is under the control of Vata vriddhi. In everyday practise, it is frequently encountered. Due to hesitation in following Sutika Paricharya, she may suffer immediately

during Sutika kala by Sutika rogas or afterwards by diseases like Pandu, Raktapradar, Sandhishool, katishula etc.

Acharya Kashyap discussed puerperal disorders twice: once in Dushprajata Chikitsadhyaya and again in Sutikopakramaniya Adhyaya. The total number of disorders documented at both locations adds up to 74.

SUTIKA ROGA NIDAN

Sutika Awastha janya Dhatukshay, Vataprakop and Agnimandya along with failure to follow Sutika Paricharya simultaneously leads To various Sutika Rogas.

SAMPRAPTI^[2]**SAMPRAPTI GHATAK**

- Dosha – Kaphanubandhi vata, especially Prasuti Marut and Kapha
- Dushya- Rasa, Rakta, Artava, Mansa, Asthi and Majja
- Strotasa- Artavavaha
- Strotodushti- Vataprakopa-Margavrodhjanya and Dhatukshayajanya
- Agni- Jatharagni
- Udbhavsthan:- Udar, Kati, Garbhashaya
- Vyaktaroopa:- Shool
- Sadhya Asadhyatva:- Kashtasadhya

LOW BACKACHE IN POST- PARTUM PERIOD

Puerperium is defined as the time from the delivery of the placenta through the first few weeks after the delivery. This period is usually considered to be 6 weeks in duration. Hormonal and biological changes during pregnancy and childbirth can take a toll on a woman's body and they can take a few months to fully recover from them but if the low back ache during pregnancy and after delivery (postpartum) are ignored, it could lead to a weak spine in the later years of life. More than 60 percent of women reportedly have lower back pain during pregnancy due to the lordotic compensatory posture that one develops due to the growing weight in the belly area and/or the hormonal changes.^[2]

CAUSES

The condition occurs as during pregnancy, uterus expands and weakens the abdominal muscles. Also with increased weight in the belly area as the child grows in the womb, causes a compensatory exaggerates backward curvature called lordosis. This bending of the lower spine backward, puts strain on back.^[2]

The body releases progesterone and relaxing hormones during pregnancy which help to prepare the pelvic cavity of the body for delivery by loosening the ligaments and stretching of joints.^[2]

Since these hormones stay for a few months after delivery, it leads to post-delivery or postpartum back pain. The natural 'S' curve of the spine is affected by pregnancy, and this also shifts the center of gravity.^[2]

The weight of a growing baby in the uterus can sometimes compresses the nerves exiting the spine, and this also changes the overall posture of mother.^[2]

While mothers recover from this condition after a few months, the problem doesn't correct itself after childbirth. Obesity or being overweight can put extra pressure on your back muscles, leading to chronic pain.^[2]

The fluctuating hormone levels in the post partum period cause Musculo skeletal issues such as excessive joint motility, weakness of core stabilizers, altered spinal mobility and function.^[2]

TREATMENT

1. Nidan Parivarjan.
2. Following Sutika Paricharya.
3. Vatahara dravya, Snehan, Swedan.
4. Jeevaniya, Bruhaniya, Balavardhak and Vatahara drugs.^[2]

Samanya Sutika Paricharya – The Sutika paricharya is described in Ayurvedic texts with a particular mode in a stipulated period. The life of pregnant women is one of the most crucial period of her life. The sarva shareera dhatu of mother will be in sheetilaavastha because of growth and development of fetus in her. This is further added by Pravahana Vedana and Kleda Raktha srava during delivery. Hence the woman is with Shunya Shareera because of

Prasava vedana and she is prone to Sutika rogas. The Sutika Paricharya itself helps in punar navikarana of her body. Hence Sutika Paricharya not only supports the women but also prevents Sutika rogas. After delivery there is vitiation of Vata, expulsion of fetus, loss of fluid, and exhaustion during labour are responsible for Dhatukshaya and during this period even a minor ailment can cause a lot of harm to the body.^[3]

Ayurveda has suggested a very good protocol during Sutika kala which includes a detailed description of Ahara (nutrition), Vihara (life style), and Aushadhi (medicine) to maintain the health of the women.^[3]

Sutika Paricharya is divided into three major components as follows.

- Aashwasana (Psychological Reassurance)
- Aahara (Normal diet in puerperium)
- Vihara (Normal daily activities and therapeutic Procedures).^[3]

Regimens which are beneficial for preventing sutika katishula are:

1. **Abhyanga:** Massage with Til Taila, Bala Taila and Swedana. Abhyanga is a Vatashamak procedure.
2. **Parisheka & Avagaha-** Parisheka is pouring hot water in a stream.^[3]
3. **Udaraveshtana (Patta Bandana)**
4. **Yoni Dhupana** – Bala taila
5. **Prasuta Snana:** Hot water bath in morning & evening.^[3]

General principles of treatment for puerperal disorders

- ✦ Aetiological factors should be avoided
- ✦ Woman should be given Snehan & Swedan which suppresses Vayu.
- ✦ Sutika should take rice-gruel treated with appetizing drug.
- ✦ Sutika should be treated with Snehana, decoction prepared with Madhura, Vatahar, Jeevaniya, Brumhaniya drugs along with specific dietetics.^[4]

Pathya

Sutika Should bath with hot water or warm water.

Drink boiled water

Adequate sleep.

Udaravesthana should be done.

Abhyanga should be done with lukewarm oils.^[4]

Vegetables like Kushmanda (pumpkin), Mulak (radish) must be stirfried in ghee and used.^[4]

Apathya: Vyayaam, Krodh, Maithun, Shital Jal, Shital Vayu, Divaswap, Aatapsevana, Panchakarma.^[4]

Clinical Significance of Sutika Paricharya

During Sutika Avastha, Agni is Manda so Agnideepana Chikitsa is required after delivery. After delivery Agnivardhak drugs are used with Sneha that suppresses Vata. According to Bala of Agni Yava, Kola Laghuannapaana is advised. Mamsa Rasa is given to replenish dhatu. Brimhana Dravyas are given. By using Ushnodak Parisechan or bath is helpful for Agnideepan that helps in Snehapachan.

Thus, during Sutika Awastha Yogya Aahar helps in preventing Sutika Roga by bringing Dosha Satmya and help in Dhatuvarhdhana. If Agni is good or Balwaan, all types of Sutika Roga can be avoided.^[4]

Other measures which can be followed are

- 1- Correct posture - Pregnant women tend to slump their shoulders and arch their back as their belly grows, which puts more strain on the spine. If they sit most of the day, which is most common in case of women working from home nowadays, be sure to take regular small walks and stand up straight.^[2]
- 2- Exercise regularly – Puerperal woman may feel like lying in the bed when back hurts, but that could further aggravate the condition. A little bit of exercise may be just what they need. However, they need to be careful while exercising as in some conditions, they may have to limit their activity or skip exercise altogether.^[2]
- 3- Maintain a normal body weight - Pregnancy often leads to weight gain, so puerperal woman should try to get back to normal weight after two to three month delivery. For achieving a normal or healthy body weight, a correct diet is very important after pregnancy. Diet should include fresh vegetable, fruits, and protein along with right nutrition and regular exercise and Yoga.^[2]
- 4- Many puerperal woman suffer from low back pain for upto 6 months to 1 year. Hence it should be treated properly to enjoy their motherhood and to take care of their new born.^[2]

2. DISCUSSION

Many postpartum women complain about Katishool. It is caused by a vitiated Apana Vayu. Vitiated Vata is caused by etiological factors such as Margavrodhajanya and Dhatukshaya. Sutika Paricharya has been recommended by Acharyas to treat vitiated doshas. Thus, Vatahara Chikitsa such as Snehan, Swedan, and others are administered in Sutika to minimise Katishool. In modern practice, physiotherapy has been recommended for Low backache in post partum period. But Ayurveda has described, Snehan and Swedan for Katishool.

Abhyanga

Abhyanga given to Sutika may be Sthanika (udara or yoni) or Sarvadaihika with the help of Ghrita and Taila especially with Til Taila or BalaTaila as they get absorbed deeper into the tissues ligaments. It is Vatasanshamaka, Rasayana to Mamsadhathu, Shramahara. Abhyanga tones up the pelvic floor, abdominal, back muscle, tissues and relieve the muscle spasm and promotes strength and flexibility. Abhyanga at lower back helps for proper drainage of lochia. Yoni Abhyanga tones up vagina and perineum and prevents laxity and prolapse, alleviates pain and heals vaginal and perineal wounds.^[3]

Parisheka & Avagaha

Parisheka is pouring hot water in a stream, it is vatakapahara, vedanahara, twakaprasannata, srotoniramalata, so that abnormal blood clots accumulated in uterine cavity after the delivery of Garbha excreted properly and Vata Dosha also subsides.^[3]

Udaraveshtana (Patta Bandana)

It prevents vitiation of vatadosha by compressing hollow space produced after expulsion of foetus. Abdomen should be tightly wrapped with long cotton cloth after bath. It provides support to the back & abdomen. It mainly helps the uterus to shrink back to its normal size.^[3]

Women who undergo Cesarean section develop backache because of anesthesia given.

Sutika paricharya can also be practised after a cesarean section. Abhyanga, parisheka, udar Patta Bandhan can be done after removal of sutures which helps to support the back as well as abdomen and helps in vitiation of Vata and kapha which in turn reduces backache.

Yoni Dhupana

This will maintain the hygiene of the perineum. It keeps episiotomy site healthy, fastens its healing process. puerperal woman should always sit in small chair covered with leather bag filled with hot Bala Taila.^[3]

Mode of action of diet & drugs**Snehapana**

The Sneha (Ghrita/ Taila / Vasa/ Majja) given to sutika is mixed with dravyas like Pippali, Pippalimoola, Chavya, Chitraka, Shringavera, Yavani, Upakunchika. Ghrita is Vata pitta shamak, Balya, Rasayan, Agnideepak, Raktavikarnashak, & Yogavahi. Ghrita provides many essential fatty acids such as omega 6 which provides anti- inflammatory properties. It also contains vitamins K,E,D,A.^[3]

Garbhashaya Shodhana - Drugs like Panchakola are given for excretion of DushtaShonita from uterus. These drugs having the garbhashayashodhak & garbhashayasankochak properties, removes the dushta shonita from garbhashaya. This may facilitate uterine stimulation inducing contraction which may result in expulsion of residual blood clots.^[3]

Sneha Yavagu or Ksheerayavagu

Yavagupana in the form of manda, peya with sneha or kwatha stimulate the agni, it is grahi, laghu in nature, dhatuposhana, properties, easily digestible & absorbable, reduces thirst thus does the maintenance of water in the body. Ksheera is rich source of proteins, vitamins and calcium provides energy & maintains tissue.^[3]

Yusha

Yusha is given to the Sutika is prepared of Yava, Kola, Kulatha. It act as agnideepaka, balya, swedajanana, pusti sukhaprasadana.

Mamsa Rasa-Meat is an excellent source of iron, Vitamins, essential amino acids and trace elements. Madhura, Brimhaniya drugs are anabolic and helpful to recover maternal system from stress and strain of labour and help in galactogenesis and enhance the property of maternal milk.^[3]

Drugs

Pippali, Pippalimula, Chavya, Chitraka, Shringavera are Ushna, Teekshna, Deepana, Pachana,

Shulaghna & Kaphavatashamaka, so it is helpful in reducing Agnimandya & shoola in sutika.^[3] These drugs are katurasatmaka & katuvipaki and has the properties of shonitasanghat bhedana leads to normal yonigatasrava because of this garbhashayashuddhi occurs.

3. CONCLUSION

Pain impairs their mobility and capacity to carry out regular tasks. The pain is significant and could continue for several days.

As a result, Acharya Kashyap defined Katishula as distinct illnesses in Sutika. These conditions are caused by a vitiated Vata. Agnimandya, Margavrodh, Apararpana, and Dhatukshaya aggravate Vata. Thus, giving Sutika Vatahara Chikitsa decreases Katishula. In Ayurveda for Sutika Sutika Paricharya has been described. As Agni is Manda during Sutika Awastha, Sutika Roga occurs that's why proper management of Ahara should be given so that it will lead to Agnivardhan which helps in avoiding Sutika Roga and further it also helps in dosha Prashaman and brings all elements of body in pre-pregnancy stage.

Thus, by following Sutika Paricharya it helps in Agnivardhan, Pachana, vatashaman, Stanyavardhan, Raktavardha, Garbhashayshodhan, Yonisanrakshan, Dhatuposhan, Kostashodhan, Balavardhan, Punarnavekarana.^[3]

REFERENCES

1. Ayurvediya Prasuti Tantra Evum Stree Roga, Professor P. V. Tiwari, Chaukhambha orientalia, Varanasi, chapter 9, page 543.
2. D. K. B. A. p. D. M. S. G. Dr. Shruti Sanjay Buva, "Conceptual Study Of Sutika Shool," *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL AND MEDICAL RESEARCH*, 2024; 11(1).
3. D. V. M. D. N. K. D. S. ., D. P. K. Dr . Mamta Kumari, "AN AYURVEDIC CONCEPT OF SUTIKA PARICHARYA," *WORLD JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL AND MEDICAL RESEARCH*, 2024; 10(1).
4. U. J. Metangale A., "Importance of sutika paricharya : A review," *Journal of ayurveda and integrated medical sciences*, 2022.
5. Pawar.D.D,Gholap S., "the sutika katishoola nidan panchaka and chikitsa sutra(treatment principles) SAccording to Ayurveda A review," *ayurline: Internationa Journal Of Research in Indian Medicine*, June 2020; vol. 4.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Ayurvediya Prasuti Tantra Evum Stree Roga, Professor P. V. Tiwari, Chaukhambha orientalia, Varanasi, chapter 9, page 543.
2. D. K. B. A. p. D. M. S. G. Dr. Shruti Sanjay Buva, "Conceptual Study Of Sutika Shool," *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL AND MEDICAL RESEARCH*, 2024; 11(1).
3. D. V. M. D. N. K. D. S., D. P. K. Dr. Mamta Kumari, "AN AYURVEDIC CONCEPT OF SUTIKA PARICHARYA," *WORLD JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL AND MEDICAL RESEARCH*, 2024; 10(1).
4. U. J. Metangale A., "Importance of sutika paricharya : A review," *Journal of ayurveda and integrated medical sciences*, 2022.
5. Pawar.D.D., Gholap S., "the sutika katishoola nidana panchaka and chikitsa sutra(treatment principles) SAccording to Ayurveda A review," *ayurline: Internationa Journal Of Research in Indian Medicine*, June 2020; 4.